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БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ | JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

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INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF DENTAL REHABILITATION OF PATIENTS WITH COMPLETE ADENTIA

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ANNOTATION

It is known that in 100% of cases, after secondary dental adentia, the alveolar bone begins to atrophy. Within 3 years after tooth extraction, the alveolar bone, deprived of its main supporting function, decreases by 40-60% compared to its full size. Bone atrophy after tooth extraction creates serious difficulties in the orthopedic treatment of patients using fully removable dentures. Despite the fact that in recent years the problem of bone atrophy after tooth loss has been widely considered, it has not yet been solved, and issues such as fixation and fixation of fully removable dentures, ensuring their stabilization, have not lost their relevance in prosthetics.

Key words: atrophy, alveolar bone, fully removable prostheses, resorption, fixation, stabilization.

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TO'LIQ IKKILAMCHI ADENTIYASI BOR BEMORLARNI TISHLAR QATORI REABILITATSIYASI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH

ANNOTATSIYA

Ma'lumki, 100% hollarda tishlarning ikkilamchi adentiyasidan keyin alveolyar suyak atrofiyaga uchrab boshlaydi. Tish uzilgandan keyin 3 yil ichida asosiy qo'llab-quvvatlash funktsiyasidan mahrum bo'lgan alveolyar suyak to'liq hajmiga nisbatan 40-60% ga kamayishi kuzatiladi. Tish uzilgandan keyin suyak to'qimalarining atrofiyasi to'liq olinadigan protezlardan foydalangan holda bemorlarni ortopedik davolashda jiddiy qiyinchiliklarni keltirib chiqaradi. So'nggi yillarda tish yo'qotilgandan keyin suyak to'qimalarining atrofiyasi muammosi keng ko'lamda ko'rib chiqilayotganiga qaramay, u bugungi kungacha hal qilinmagan va to'liq olinadigan protezlarni mahkamlash va fiksatsiyalash, stabilizatsiyasini ta'minlash kabi masalalari protezlashda o'z ahamiyatini yo'qotmagan.

Kalit so'zlar: atrofiya, alveolyar suyak, to'liq olinadigan protezlar, rezorbsiya, fiksatsiya, stabilizatsiya.

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ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ РЕАБИЛИТАЦИИ ПАЦИЕНТОВ ПРИ ПОЛНОЙ АДЕНТИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Известно, что в 100% случаев после вторичной адентии зубов начинает атрофироваться альвеолярная кость. В течение 3 лет после удаления зуба альвеолярная кость, лишенная основной опорной функции, уменьшается на 40-60% по сравнению с ее полным размером. Атрофия костной ткани после удаления зуба создает серьезные трудности при ортопедическом лечении больных с использованием полностью съемных протезов. Несмотря на то, что в последние годы широко рассматривается проблема атрофии костной ткани после потери зуба, она до сих пор не решена, и такие вопросы, как фиксация и фиксация полностью съемных протезов, обеспечение их стабилизации, не утратили своей актуальности в протезировании.

Ключевые слова: атрофия, альвеолярная кость, полностью съемные протезы, резорбция, фиксация, стабилизация.

Kirish: So'nggi yillarda alveolyar o'siq va yuz-jag' suyak to'qimasi atrofiyasi haqida tadqiqotlar olib borilishiga qaramasdan, bugungi kungacha bu muammo hal qilinmagan, ammo to'liq olinadigan protezlarni mahkamlash va fiksatsiyalash, stabilizatsiyalash masalalari protezlashda o'z ahamiyatini yo'qotmagan. Hozirgi vaqtda to'liq olinadigan protezlar bilan protezlash sharoitlarini yaxshilash va alveolyar suyak to'qimalarining hajmini oshirish uchun operatsiyalarda qo'llaniladigan usullar va materiallar taklif qilingan [10, 11]. Shunga qaramay, to'liq olinadigan protezlarni sifatli mahkamlash va barqarorlashtirishga erishish har doim ham mumkin emas, chunki jag'ni atrofiyalangan sohalarida implantatsiyani amalga oshirish [1, 2] yoki alveolyar suyak hajmining kamayishi bilan implantatsiya materiallar bir vaqtning o'zida ortishi, ya'ni dental implantatsiya uchun ko'rsatmalari kengayib borishiga sabab bo'lmoqda.

To'liq ikkilamchi adentiyaning yuqorigi jag'da ko'rinishi

Tadqiqot maqsadi: Tishlarni to'liq yo'qotgan suyak to'qimalarining og'ir atrofiyasi bo'lgan olinadigan protezlar bilan davolanadigan bemorlarni ortopedik davolash natijalarini baholash.

Materiallar va tadqiqot usullari: Tadqiqot uchun 35 yoshdan yuqori va pastki jag'larda tishlari to'liq yo'qligi (to'liq adentiya) bo'lgan 35 nafar bemor tanlangan.

53 yoshdan 82 yoshgacha, 16 nafar bemorda yuqori jag'da to'liq adentiya, Shreder bo'yicha 3-tur bilan tavsiflangan, ya'ni yuqori jag'da alveolyar jarayon butunlay yo'q, yuqori jag'ning tanasining o'lchamlari keskin kichraygan, yomon rivojlangan alveolyar tuberkulyarlar, tekis tanglay.

21 nafar bemorning pastki jag'ida to'liq adentiya Keller bo'yicha 2-turi bilan tavsiflangan, ya'ni pastki jag'ning alveolyar qismining keskin bir xil atrofiyasi, harakatlanuvchi shilliq qavat alveolyar tizma darajasida joylashgan. To'liq adentiya bilan og'rigan barcha bemorlar 3 guruhga bo'lingan. Birinchi guruhga an'anaviy usul bo'yicha to'liq olinadigan protezlar qilingan 13 nafar bemor kirdi. Ikkinchi guruhga intraosseus implantlarga qo'shimchalar bilan o'rnatiladigan olinadigan protezlarni olgan 10 nafar bemor kiradi. Uchinchi guruhga 12 kishi kirdi.

Dental implantlarga o'rnatilgan protezlarni olgan bemorlar, bir vaqtning o'zida suyakni mustahkamlash orqali alveolyar suyak to'qimalarining hajmini oshiradi. Birinchi guruh bemorlarida ortopedik davolash natijalari quyidagilarga qarab ijobiy yoki salbiy deb hisoblanadi:

- 1 - moslashish davri;
- 2 - protezlarni mahkamlash (sinov) va stabilizatsiya darajasi;
- 3 - turli xil ovqatlarni iste'mol qilish imkoniyati.

Ikkinchi va uchinchi guruhlarda, yuqoridagi mezonlarga qo'shimcha ravishda, implantatsiyaning samaradorligi qo'shimcha ravishda baholandi [2]. Implantlarning ishlash samaradorligi mezoni aniqlandi, ball tizimi bo'yicha:

1.0 - implant klinik jihatdan harakatsiz yoki uning harakatchanligi ichida to'qimalarning fiziologik muvofiqligi; tish milki, suyak cho'ntaklarining yallig'lanishi, implant chegarasi sohasida og'riq va zarar yo'q; implant tish protezi uchun tayanch sifatida to'liq funktsional bosimni ko'taradi.

0,75 – milkda paydo bo'ladigan yallig'lanish, yengil bloklanmagan implantning harakatchanligi; suyak cho'ntaklari yo'q.

0,5 - implant atrofidagi milklarning surunkali yallig'lanishi belgilari, klinik jihatdan aniqlangan harakatchanlik, suyak cho'ntaklarining mavjudligi, mustahkamlab turuvchi implantatsiya funktsiyasi kamayadi.

0,25 - yallig'lanishning aniq belgilari, harakatchanlik va chuqurlikning mavjudligi suyak cho'ntaklari borligi.

0 - implantni o'rab turgan suyak to'qimalarining to'liq yo'qolishi va uning jag'dan granulyatsiyalar bilan siljishi.

Implantlarning paydo bo'lish chastotasi (%) PFI qiymati 1,0; P0.75, P0.5, P0.25, P0 - mos ravishda PFI 0,75, 0,5 qiymati bilan, 0,25, 0, bu formula bilan aniqlandi: $P1.0 = [a1.0-n] \times 100$ va boshqalar,

bu erda n - bemorlarning ushbu guruhiga o'rnatilgan implantlar soni; a1.0 - qiymatga ega bo'lgan implantlar soni PFI 1.0; a0,75, a0,5, a0,25, a0 - mos ravishda bilan implantlar sonini ifodalaydi

PFI qiymati 0,75, 0,5, 0,25, 0. Barcha bemorlar uchun kuzatuv davri uch guruh 1 yoshdan 5 yoshgacha bo'lgan.

Tadqiqot natijalari: Protezni og'iz bo'shlig'idagi fiksatsiyasi qoniqarsiz bo'lganda, bemorlarning 50 foizida Shrederga ko'ra 3-toifa, Keller bo'yicha 2-toifa to'liq olinadigan protezlar bilan protezlar bilan.

Birinchi guruhni to'liq olinadigan protezlarni mahkamlash va fiksatsiya darajasi qoniqtirmadi va shuning uchun ular turli xil oziq-ovqatlardan foydalanishda cheklangan. Protezlarga moslashish davri 1 oydan 1,5 oygacha davom etdi va bemorlar tomonidan toqat qilish qiyin edi. 2 va 3-guruhlardagi barcha bemorlarda protezlarga moslashish davri 3 haftadan oshmadi va bemorlar tomonidan osonlikcha toqat qilindi. To'liq olinadigan protezlarning implantlariga mexanik mahkamlash protezlashdan so'ng darhol va uzoq muddatda mahkamlash va fiksatsiya bo'yicha testlar davomida ijobiy baho olishga imkon berdi.

Xulosa: To'liq olinadigan protezlarning og'iz bo'shlig'ida fiksatsiyasi, chaynash va nutq funksiyalarini samaraliroq tiklash uchun, bizning tadqiqotlarimiz shuni ko'rsatdiki, an'anaviy protezlashning salbiy natijalari bilan, qo'shimcha fiksatsiya usullaridan foydalangan, olinadigan protezlardan kengroq foydalanish kerak.

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9 ЖИЛД, 5 СОН

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